

Neutronic and Burnup Analysis of TRISO Fuel Homogenization in a Sodium-Cooled Microreactor with Monte Carlo Code OpenMC

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ABSTRACT

The growing demand for clean and reliable energy, accelerated by the rapid expansion of artificial intelligence and data-driven technologies, has intensified interest in advanced microreactors as scalable, carbon-free power sources. Among these designs, TRISO-particle dispersed fuels offer inherent safety, high burnup capability, and extended core lifetimes, making them particularly attractive for next-generation deployment. Accurate neutronic modeling of TRISO fuel is essential; however, explicit simulation of billions of layered TRISO particles in Monte Carlo codes is computationally expensive for full core studies. In this work, four homogenization methods are evaluated for the Sodium-cooled TRISO-fueled Advanced Reactor (STAR) using the state-of-the-art Monte Carlo code OpenMC, with emphasis on their accuracy and computational efficiency relative to fully explicit models. The Improved and Hybrid Reactivity Equivalent Physical Transformation methods (IRPT and HRPT) demonstrate excellent agreement, with k_{eff} deviations of only 6 pcm and 11 pcm, respectively, while achieving $\times 12$ – 13 speedups. Neutron flux and power distributions remain within 3% at both beginning and end-of-life, and burnup calculations over a 20 year lifetime show k_{eff} deviations below 120 pcm. In contrast, the Kernel-Layered Matrix Reactivity method (KLMR-M2 and M3) shows larger discrepancies, with k_{eff} differences of up to 1800 pcm for KLMR-M2 and 550 pcm for KLMR-M3 at the end of the cycle, along with flux deviations of 8%, and power distribution differences of 6%. The results provide a foundation for extending homogenization methods to coupled multiphysics studies and transient analysis of TRISO-fueled microreactors.

Keywords: TRISO, microreactors, Homogenization methods, OpenMC, burnup

1. INTRODUCTION

Nuclear microreactors are emerging worldwide as a promising technology to address the growing demand for reliable, carbon-free energy. With their compact size and inherent safety features, microreactors are designed to provide reliable electricity where conventional generation is impractical. Many advanced microreactor concepts currently under development rely on TRISO (TRi-structural ISOtropic) coated particle fuel as their enabling technology, including the eVinciTM reactor by Westinghouse Electric Company and the Micro Modular Reactor (MMRTM) from Ultra Safe Nuclear Corporation. In addition, TRISO fuel has been successfully demonstrated in experimental reactors such as China's 10 MW_{th} pebble-bed High Temperature Reactor (HTR-10) [1] and Japan's 30 MW_{th} prismatic High Temperature Test Reactor (HTTR) [2]. TRISO fuel is particularly well suited to the mission of microreactors because of its inherent retention of fission products, tolerance to high temperatures, and ability to sustain long operating lifetimes with minimal refueling. A typical TRISO particle consists of a central fuel kernel surrounded by four protective layers: a porous buffer, inner pyrolytic carbon (IPyC), silicon carbide (SiC), and outer pyrolytic carbon (OPyC). While the performance benefits of TRISO fuel are well established, its double-heterogeneous nature poses significant challenges for high-fidelity neutronic modeling and simulation (M&S).

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To address these challenges, several methods have been proposed in the reactor physics community over the past decades. One approach is the Woodcock delta-tracking method [3], implemented in codes such as Serpent [4] and MONK [5]. However, this method requires substantial source-code modifications to implement in OpenMC. A more widely applied approach is homogenization. The simplest baseline is the volume homogenization method [6], where material properties are averaged according to constituent volume fractions. While computationally straightforward, this method neglects spatial self-shielding and can introduce large errors in systems with dispersed particles. To improve accuracy, Kim [7] proposed the Reactivity Equivalent Physical Transformation (RPT) method, which captures double heterogeneity more effectively but still shows notable deviations when applied to fuels containing burnable poisons. Li et al. later introduced the Improved RPT (IRPT) method [8], which extends applicability to systems with both fuel and poison particles, though significant errors remain for large particle sizes or high poison fractions. Lou et al. subsequently developed the Hybrid RPT (HRPT) method [9], which combines traditional RPT with ring-based corrections to improve accuracy for such cases. In this study, alongside IRPT and HRPT, we also evaluate two additional approaches—the Kernel-Layered Matrix Reactivity methods (KLMR-M2 and KLMR-M3)—and assess their performance for the Sodium-cooled TRISO-fueled Advanced Reactor (STAR) using the OpenMC Monte Carlo code.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 describes the STAR microreactor and its components, Section 3 outlines the homogenization methods, Section 4 presents and discusses the results, and Section 5 provides conclusions and perspectives for extending this work to transient and coupled thermal-hydraulic analyses.

2. DESIGN OF STAR MICRO REACTOR

Figure 1. OpenMC model of the STAR microreactor core: (a) radial view, (b) axial view.

The STAR microreactor design is inspired by the AECL-LANL Canadian Nuclear BatteryTM (CNB) program [10]. The name ‘Nuclear Battery’ highlights the passive and solid-state feature of the core, where the graphite core block acts as a thermal energy storage cell. The current configuration corresponds to a 2.4 MW_{th} reactor with a fuel lifetime of 20 effective full power years (EFPYs). The fuel is based on TRISO-coated particles compacted into cylindrical fuel rods. The core contains approximately 522 fuel rods and 150 heat pipes arranged in a hexagonal lattice within a solid graphite moderator. The moderator is surrounded by graphite radial, top, and bottom reflectors. The nominal core operating temperature is 773 K. Heat is transferred from the fuel compacts by conduction through the graphite moderator to stainless steel heat pipes. Reactivity control is provided by 13 control rods and 6 shutdown rods containing B₄C neutron absorbers, while long-term excess reactivity is managed by incorporating burnable poison particles (Er₂O₃) within the fuel compacts. This helps in bringing the reactivity swing

for 20 years of full power operation within the limits of the reactivity control system as well as flattens the core radial flux profile. An OpenMC model of the STAR core is shown in both radial and axial views in Figure 1.

3. METHODOLOGY

Modeling TRISO fuel poses a unique challenge due to its double-heterogeneous structure. While explicit particle-level simulations in Monte Carlo codes can capture the physics with high fidelity, their computational cost becomes resource intensive for whole-core depletion studies. To overcome this, several homogenization methods have been developed to preserve the essential neutronic behavior of explicit models while drastically reducing computational burden. In this study, four such methods are investigated: the Improved Reactivity Equivalent Physical Transformation (IRPT), the Hybrid Reactivity Equivalent Physical Transformation (HRPT), and two variants of the Kernel-Layered Matrix Reactivity (KLMR) method. These methods are compared against explicit particle models using the OpenMC Monte Carlo code. The following subsections provide an overview of each method.

3.1. Improved RPT (IRPT)

The IRPT and HRPT methods are extensions of the Reactivity Equivalent Physical Transformation (RPT) method originally introduced by Kim [7]. In the RPT framework, a reference calculation is first performed with an explicitly modeled fuel pin, and its multiplication factor k_{eff} is recorded. A homogenized pin-cell model is then created by reducing the fuel radius and surrounding it with an annular region of graphite matrix. The effective radius of the homogenized fuel pin is iteratively tuned until the k_{eff} of the homogenized model reproduces the reference value.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the Improved Reactivity Equivalent Physical Transformation (IRPT) method.

The IRPT method [8] builds upon this concept by separating the effects of fuel and burnable poison particles. In the first step, all burnable poisons are removed, and the equivalent RPT radius is determined from the fuel-only system. Once this effective fuel radius is found, the inner-zone radius is subsequently adjusted until the k_{eff} value reproduces that of the explicit model. The overall procedure is illustrated schematically in Figure 2.

3.2. Hybrid RPT (HRPT)

The Hybrid RPT (HRPT) method [9] combines the traditional RPT procedure with the Ring RPT (RRPT) method. In RRPT, dispersed particle material is compressed into a ring consisting solely of the material of the dispersed particle. HRPT first applies the RPT method to obtain an equivalent radius for the fuel-only system, after removing burnable poisons. The poison particles are then reintroduced, and RRPT is applied to represent them as an equivalent annular region within the first RPT radius. This process generates four concentric zones: matrix, fuel–matrix mixture, poison ring, and fuel–matrix mixture, as

illustrated in Fig. 3. This layered representation enhances the treatment of burnable poisons in double-heterogeneous systems while retaining the efficiency of the RPT approach.

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the Hybrid Reactivity Equivalent Physical Transformation (HRPT) method.

3.3. Kernel-Layered Matrix Reactivity (KLMR)

The Kernel-Layered Matrix Reactivity method introduces a modified treatment of the surrounding matrix. After removing burnable poison particles, the graphite matrix is divided into two (KLMR-M2) or three (KLMR-M3) subregions. The volume of the inner matrix zone is then adjusted by searching for the smallest reactivity difference, $|\Delta k|$, using the JAYA optimization algorithm [11]. In this method, TRISO fuel kernels remain individually represented, while the surrounding buffer, pyrolytic carbon, and silicon carbide layers are homogenized to form a composite “sandwich-like” structure. The RRPT procedure is subsequently applied to determine an equivalent poison ring within this homogenized region, as illustrated in Figure 4. The two variants are shown separately in Figure 4 (a) for KLMR-M2 and Figure 4 (b) for KLMR-M3.

Figure 4. Schematic representation of the Kernel-Layered Matrix Reactivity (KLMR) method.

3.4. Simulation Parameters

All neutronic and depletion simulations were carried out using OpenMC version 0.15.2 [12], an open-source, high-fidelity Monte Carlo code originally developed at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology and now maintained by ANL and a broad international community. OpenMC is written in modern C++ and Python, providing advanced geometry modeling through constructive solid geometry (CSG) and support for continuous-energy cross sections. Parallel execution is supported through both MPI and OpenMP, making it suitable for large-scale high-performance computing.

For this study, all calculations used the ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data library [13]. To ensure consistency, 1×10^6 particle histories per cycle were simulated with 400 active cycles following 100 inactive cycles for source convergence. Burnup calculations employed the predictor–corrector method. Each case was executed with 32 CPU cores, distributed across 10 MPI tasks on 5 nodes of the Compute Canada cluster Cedar.

4. RESULTS

The performance of the homogenization methods was first assessed by comparing the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}) against the fully explicit TRISO model. The results are summarized in Table I. Both IRPT and HRPT reproduced the reference value with excellent agreement, differing by only 6 pcm and 11 pcm, respectively. By contrast, the KLMR methods showed noticeably larger discrepancies: KLMR-M3 differed by 241 pcm, while KLMR-M2 exhibited the largest deviation at 792 pcm.

Table I. Comparison of k_{eff} values for explicit and homogenized models.

Model	$k_{\text{eff}} (\pm 1\sigma)$	Δk (pcm)
Explicit	1.02934 ± 0.00008	–
IRPT	1.02940 ± 0.00007	6
HRPT	1.02923 ± 0.00007	11
KLMR-M2	1.03726 ± 0.00007	792
KLMR-M3	1.03175 ± 0.00007	241

Figure 5. Wall clock run times and speedup achieved for TRISO fuel homogenization methods.

In addition to accuracy, computational efficiency was evaluated by measuring wall-clock runtimes relative to the explicit model. The achieved speedups are shown in Figure 5. The IRPT and HRPT methods demonstrated the highest performance gains, with reductions in runtime of approximately a factor of 12 and 13, respectively. The KLMR methods also provided substantial improvements, with speedups of 11× for KLMR-M2 and 10× for KLMR-M3.

Figure 6 shows the thermal neutron flux comparison between the explicit model and the homogenized cases. Both IRPT and HRPT reproduced the reference flux distribution with excellent agreement, with deviations ranging from about 0.3% to 2.3% for IRPT and 0.5% to 1.8% for HRPT. In contrast, the KLMR approaches showed larger discrepancies: KLMR-M2 exhibited deviations between -0.7% and 5.5% , while KLMR-M3 ranged from -4.3% to 3.2% . A similar trend is observed for the power distribution, shown in Figure 7, where IRPT and HRPT remain within about $\pm 2\%$ of the explicit model, while KLMR-M2 and KLMR-M3 show much larger deviations, up to 4%.

Figure 8 shows the evolution of k_{eff} over 20 EFPYs, with effective multiplication factor values shown on

Figure 6. Thermal neutron flux comparison between explicit and homogeneous models

the left and deviations relative to the explicit model on the right. At the start of the cycle, k_{eff} decreases sharply due to the strong absorption effect of burnable poisons (Er_2O_3). As those burnable poisons deplete, their absorption effect diminishes, and the reactivity decline slows because the rate of negative reactivity insertion from the poisons becomes small. Past that initial phase, the dominant factors become fissile fuel depletion and buildup of fission product poisons, leading to a more gradual and steady decline of k_{eff} throughout the rest of the 20-year cycle. Among the homogenization methods, IRPT and HRPT reproduce the explicit reference most accurately, with deviations staying below 300 pcm and 410 pcm, respectively. KLMR-M3 shows errors, up to about 1100 pcm, while KLMR-M2 diverges the most, reaching nearly 1850 pcm at the end-of-life.

Figure 9 presents the relative differences in key actinide and fission product concentrations at end-of-cycle between the explicit and homogenized models. For the actinides, IRPT and HRPT reproduce the reference with very high fidelity, maintaining deviations within about 1%. By contrast, the KLMR methods introduce significantly larger errors, especially for transuranics such as ^{239}Pu , ^{241}Pu , and ^{241}Am , where KLMR-M2 overestimates concentrations by more than 10%. In the case of fission products, IRPT and HRPT remain highly consistent with the explicit model, with deviations on the order of tenths of a percent for most nuclides. The KLMR-M2 method, however, shows substantial departures, reaching 7% for ^{109}Ag and 5–6% for ^{107}Pd and ^{106}Ru .

5. CONCLUSIONS

Accurate modeling of TRISO-fueled reactors at the particle level provides the highest fidelity but quickly becomes computationally costly for full-core depletion studies. Homogenization methods offer a prac-

Figure 7. Power distribution comparison between explicit and homogeneous models

Figure 8. Evolution of k_{eff} over 20 EFPYs and difference relative to the explicit model.

tical alternative by simplifying the double-heterogeneous fuel structure into a single-heterogeneous system without substantial source-code modifications, thereby improving computational performance. In this work, four homogenization methods, IRPT, HRPT, KLMR-M2, and KLMR-M3, were assessed against fully explicit model of the STAR sodium-cooled micro reactor using the OpenMC Monte Carlo code. The comparisons covered k_{eff} , neutron flux and power distributions, long-term burnup behavior,

Figure 9. Comparison of isotopic inventories between explicit and homogenized models at end-of-cycle (EOC).

and isotopic inventories over a 20-year operating lifetime.

The results demonstrate that the IRPT and HRPT methods achieve excellent fidelity while offering substantial computational time, with k_{eff} deviations below 300 pcm and 410 pcm, flux and power differences within 3%, and isotopic concentrations closely matching the reference (within about 1%). By contrast, the KLMR methods introduced larger discrepancies: KLMR-M3 deviated by up to 1100 pcm in k_{eff} and showed errors of several percent in flux, power, and isotopic inventories, while KLMR-M2 exhibited the poorest agreement, exceeding 1800 pcm in k_{eff} and more than 10% for some actinides. Nevertheless, all four methods reduced runtimes substantially compared to the explicit model, achieving speedups between 10 \times and 13 \times . Future work will extend this assessment to coupled multiphysics simulations and transient analyses, where the fidelity of homogenization methods will play an even more critical role.

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